

Horizon Europe

D7.9 Report on iRead4Skills Use

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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the use of the iRead4Skills system performed in the context of training, co-creation and development tasks, supervised testing and autonomous online access. These activities encompass a wide range of initiatives, from large-scale accredited training sessions and hands-on workshops to systematic application testing with educators and adult learners.

The iRead4Skills project aims to develop an intelligent reading improvement system that evaluates text complexity and suggests appropriate reading materials for adult learners with low literacy levels. The monitoring of the use and testing of the tools, led by MEC in collaboration with UNL, INESC ID, UAB and UCLouvain partners, and a network of cooperating Adult Learning (AL) and Vocational Education Training (VET) schools and professionals, shows remarkable success in engaging the educational community.

The tailored training programme achieved outstanding participation, with **over 420 educators** attending the sessions. These participants came not only from mainland Portugal but also from the autonomous regions of Madeira and the Azores, as well as from Portuguese-speaking countries including Brazil, Angola, Guinea-Bissau, and Mozambique. This international reach demonstrates the widespread interest in tools for text complexity classification and adaptation for adult education.

In Portugal, the network of 7 partner schools with signed protocols provided the institutional framework for sustained engagement with educators. The co-creation session held at UNL in February 2025 brought together 13 teachers with technical specialists from INESC and MEC, ensuring that the application development was firmly grounded in real classroom needs and pedagogical requirements.

The system testing programme involved systematic evaluation phases across all partner countries, beginning with the testing of the text classifier in the context of co-creation for development stages, in May 2025, and culminating in the comprehensive testing of the prototypes from December 2025 to January 2026. A **total of 423 participants** across three countries contributed to this use-validation effort: in Belgium, 177 adult learners and 20 trainers; in Portugal, 73 learners and 59 trainers; and in Spain, 54 learners and 40 teachers. The cross-national testing ensured that the tools were validated across different educational contexts and relevant linguistic environments.

Country	Belgium	Portugal	Spain
Participant profile			
Median Age	34 years	31.7 years	26.3 years
gender distribution (female %)	62.7%	60%	74%
Satisfaction Levels	High	High	Clearly positive

Table 1: Participants profile and satisfaction level obtained in the wider testing phase

In total, the activities developed for user engagement reached **more than 890 participants world-wide**.

2. Introduction

2.1 Project Background

The iRead4Skills project (*Intelligent Reading Improvement System for Fundamental and Transversal Skills Development*) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation action designed to address the persistent literacy challenges among adult populations in Europe. All major indicators (e.g., OECD, PIACC) show that a significant portion of the adult population faces difficulties in interpreting functional, technical, or informative texts. This skill gap generates high systemic costs: research indicates that countries with poor literacy levels face significant economic costs - estimated between 1.2% and 2% of GDP annually - due to productivity loss, unemployment, and increased social welfare expenditure¹ (World Literacy Foundation, 2015; PwC, 2018).

The project developed an intelligent system that classifies text complexity and provides writing assistance for adapting texts to different complexity levels. The framework establishes three text complexity levels - *Very Easy*, *Easy*, and *Plain*², roughly aligned with CEFR levels A1, A2, and B1. This classification system integrates lexical, syntactic, and cohesion features to provide a robust analysis of textual complexity tailored to low-literacy adult native speakers.

The iRead4Skills system offers two main functions: the Text Classifier, which allows users to classify texts according to their complexity level, and the Writing Assistant, which helps adapt texts for pedagogical purposes or create messages more accessible to the majority of the adult population. These tools address a critical gap in available resources for adult education and literacy development.

2.2 Report Objectives

This report aims to document the activities related to the usage of the iRead4Skills application, with particular emphasis on:

- The training sessions delivered to educators and the remarkable participation achieved,
- The co-creation activities involving AL teachers and specialists,
- The systematic testing of the system prototypes and the feedback gathered.

3. Training Activities

The training programme constitutes one of the most significant achievements of the iRead4Skills implementation in what concerns user engagement. The strategic focus on Portuguese-language training reflects the unique position of the Ministry of Education (MEC) within the consortium, which provides privileged access to the target audience across Portugal's extensive adult education network. This institutional access, encompassing *Qualifica Centres* (Centres for Adult Qualification), AL schools, and VET providers nationwide, represents a substantial asset for the project, enabling effective dissemination at scale that would otherwise require years of network building. Through a strategic partnership with CENFORES - *Centros de Formação* (Training Centres), the project delivered officially accredited training sessions that attracted unprecedented participation from educators across

¹ PwC (2018). *Social cost of low literacy*. Europe Monitor, April 2018; Cree, A. (2015). *The Economic & Social Cost of Illiteracy: A Snapshot of Illiteracy in a Global Context*. World Literacy Foundation.

² Monteiro, R., Amaro, R., Correia, S., Pintard, A., Gauchola, R., Moutinho, M., & Blanco Escoda, X. (2023). *iRead4Skills - Complexity Levels (V1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10459090>; Amaro, R., Correia, S., Monteiro, R., Pintard, A., Moutinho, M., & Barbosa, S. (2025). Framework of Textual Complexity for Low-Literacy Adults: Levels and Descriptors within the iRead4skill Project. *Langues & Parole*, 10, 57–119. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/languesparole.154>

the Portuguese-speaking world. Importantly, while the training programme leveraged Portugal's institutional infrastructure, the iRead4Skills tools themselves were validated across three European countries (Belgium, Portugal, and Spain) with 423 participants, ensuring that the scientific and pedagogical foundations of the project maintain full European validity and cross-linguistic applicability.

3.1 First and second Accredited Training Sessions

The first and second major accredited training session were held online on 25 November 2024 and 29 April 2025, with a duration of 3 hours. These sessions achieved remarkable reach, attracting **312 participants** from diverse geographical locations. The participants represented:

- Mainland Portugal – educators from various regions across the country
- Autonomous Region of Madeira – teachers working with adult learners in the archipelago
- Autonomous Region of the Azores – educators from the Atlantic islands
- Brazil – professionals interested in Portuguese-language literacy tools
- Angola – educators working in adult education contexts
- Guinea-Bissau – teachers engaged in literacy programmes
- Mozambique – adult education professionals

This international participation underscores the relevance of the iRead4Skills tools beyond the Portuguese national context, demonstrating their potential applicability across the entire Lusophone world. The session introduced participants to the project's objectives, the text complexity framework, and the potential applications of the tools in adult education settings.

3.2 Third Accredited Training Session

The second accredited training session took place on 14 December 2025, again with a duration of 3 hours and delivered online. This session attracted **110 participants** from mainland Portugal, the Azores, and Madeira archipelagos. The session was led by Isabel Marques (MEC) and Susana Correia (UNL), bringing together expertise in adult education policy and technical development.

This training session had a distinctive hands-on character, focusing specifically on the practical testing of the iRead4Skills application prototype. The session structure included:

- A concise presentation of the iRead4Skills project and its objectives
- Introduction to the application prototype and its two main functions: Text Complexity Classifier and Writing Assistant
- Practical demonstration of the application's capabilities
- Hands-on testing in simultaneous breakout rooms, following a methodological observation and recording protocol
- Sharing of a pedagogical exercise designed for classroom practice

The breakout room structure allowed participants to engage directly with the application in smaller groups, facilitating more focused interaction and detailed feedback collection. The pedagogical exercise shared at the end of the session was very well received by participants, who expressed enthusiasm about applying it in their own classrooms.

The feedback from this session was overwhelmingly positive. Teachers and trainers demonstrated great interest in using the iRead4Skills application in their classrooms, both for preparing pedagogical materials and for promoting literacy among adult learners in formal and informal educational contexts. Many participants expressed eagerness to begin using the application as soon as it becomes fully available.

3.3 Training Session Summary

Date	Duration	Participants	Key Features
25 November 2024	3 hours	160	Introduction to project and framework.
29 April 2025	3 hours	152	International reach: Portugal (mainland, Madeira, Azores), Brazil, Angola, Guinea-Bissau, Mozambique. Introduction to project and framework.
14 December 2025	3 hours	110	Hands-on prototype testing in breakout rooms. Focus on Text Classification and Writing Assistant functions. Pedagogical exercises shared.
TOTAL	9 hours	422	Accredited training through CENFORES partnership

3.4 Pedagogical Events at Partner Schools

In addition to the large-scale accredited training sessions, targeted dissemination activities were conducted at in-person pedagogical events held at partner schools in July 2025. These events provided opportunities for deeper engagement with specific educational communities:

Pedagogical Days at AE Paço de Arcos: This event was directed at the entire educational community of the Paço de Arcos school cluster, including teachers, trainers, and administrative staff involved in adult education. The presentation focused on how the iRead4Skills tools could support their existing programmes and enhance the accessibility of educational materials.

Pedagogical Days at AE Adelaide Cabette: Similarly, this event engaged the Adelaide Cabette school cluster community, promoting awareness of the project and demonstrating practical applications of the text complexity classification system in adult learning contexts.

Online Coordination Meeting (January 2026): On 22 January 2026, an online meeting brought together 26 teachers from 7 partner schools to disseminate project results and prepare for the application of prototype testing with adult learners. This session served as the final coordination step before field validation, ensuring that participating educators were fully briefed on testing protocols and data collection procedures.

These targeted engagement activities, both face-to-face and online, complemented the broader training sessions by providing personalized interaction and addressing specific questions from educators already working with adult learners in their institutions.

4. Co-Creation and Development Activities

4.1 Co-Creation Session at UNL – 17 February 2025

A pivotal co-creation session was held face-to-face at UNL on 17 February 2025, bringing together specialists and educational practitioners to collaboratively shape the application's development. This session represented a cornerstone of the user-centered design approach adopted by the project.

The session brought together:

- NLP researchers from INESC-ID and Mindshaker – providing technical expertise in natural language processing and application development
- Specialists from UNL – contributing expertise in linguistics, adult education and learning technologies
- Representatives from MEC – bringing policy perspective and national literacy programme expertise
- **13 teachers from 6 partner schools – providing practical classroom experience and real-world insights.**

The participation of 13 teachers representing 6 different partner schools was particularly valuable, as it ensured that diverse educational contexts and needs were represented in the co-creation process. These teachers brought direct experience of working with adult learners with varying literacy levels, enabling them to provide concrete feedback on the application's usability, functionality, and pedagogical relevance.

The co-creation session enabled direct collaboration between technical developers and educational practitioners, ensuring that the application features were firmly grounded in real classroom needs. Participants worked together to identify priority features, discuss potential use cases, and suggest improvements to the user interface and functionality. This collaborative approach significantly enhanced the relevance and usability of the final application prototype.

4.2 Partner Schools

Throughout the project, formal protocols were established with educational centers to facilitate testing, implementation, and ongoing collaboration. The network of partner schools has been essential to the success of the training and testing activities, providing both participants and real-world testing environments.

The following schools are currently part of the iRead4Skills partner network:

- AE Paço de Arcos – one of the founding partner schools
- AE Adelaide Cabette – actively engaged in all testing phases
- AE da Moita – newly added to the network, expanding geographical coverage
- Additional schools from the Ler+ Qualifica network – contributing to broader testing and dissemination

The addition of AE da Moita to the partner network during the project period demonstrates the growing interest in the iRead4Skills tools and the project's ability to expand its reach to new educational contexts.

5. Tools Testing

The systematic testing of the iRead4Skills tools constituted a critical component of the project's development and validation process. The testing programme was designed to gather comprehensive feedback from both educators and adult learners, ensuring that the system meets the needs of its intended users.

5.1 Prototype Testing and Validation

The comprehensive prototype testing phase represented the most intensive testing effort of the project, spanning from December 2025 to the end of January 2026. This extended testing period allowed for thorough evaluation of both the Text Classifier and Writing Assistant tools in real educational settings across the partner countries.

In Portugal, a dedicated dissemination session for prototype testing was conducted on 22 January 2026, specifically focused on supporting the teachers engaged in testing. This online session brought together **23 teachers from 6 partner schools**, providing them with detailed guidance on testing procedures and gathering their initial experiences with the prototype. The testing programme strategically engaged both teachers and adult learners, recognizing that both user groups bring valuable and complementary perspectives to the evaluation process. Teachers provided feedback on the application's utility for material preparation and classroom use, while adult learners contributed insights into the accessibility and usefulness of the tools from an end-user perspective.

To ensure systematic and comprehensive data collection during the testing phases, a robust testing protocol was collaboratively designed by UCLouvain, UNL, and MEC, including specific monitoring and evaluation tools. This form enabled testers across all partner countries to document their experiences systematically, noting both strengths and areas requiring improvement. All partners participating in the testing phases contributed to the validation of successive application versions throughout the development process. The coordination of dissemination and monitoring across the different territories maintained consistent communication between country teams and, in each country, with testing participants directly, providing technical support as needed.

Summary of the actions:

Testing Phase	Period	Key Activities
Text Classification Testing	May 2025 (5 sessions)	Online sessions on 8, 21, 22, 23, and 30 May. Partner schools and Ler+ Qualifica network. Focus on classification function.
Prototype Testing	15 Dec 2025 – 27 Jan 2026	Extended testing of full prototype. Both Text Classification and Writing Assistant functions. 423 participants: Belgium, 177 adult learners and 20 trainers; Portugal, 73 learners and 59 trainers; Spain, 54 learners and 40 teachers.
Prototype Dissemination Session	22 January 2026	1.5-hour online session. 23 teachers from 6 partner schools. Guidance and initial feedback collection.

5.6 Results

The testing of the iRead4Skills tools across all three target language communities, **Belgium (French), Portugal (Portuguese), and Spain (Spanish)**, provided interesting results. Using a common evaluation protocol, the consortium assessed usability, interpretability, and pedagogical adequacy of both core application components: the **Text Classifier** and the **Writing Assistant**.

Application Components Tested

Text Classifier: Provides a global assessment of text difficulty along with local indicators of lexical, syntactic, semantic, and discourse complexity. This tool enables educators to quickly evaluate whether a text is appropriate for their learners' reading level.

Writing Assistant: Offers a fine-grained diagnosis of complexity features, helping users identify difficult sections and devise strategies for reformulation and simplification. This tool supports educators in adapting texts for specific learner groups.

User Satisfaction and Country-Specific Feedback

Across all three countries, **satisfaction levels were consistently high**. Belgium reported Likert scores ranging from 4.19 to 4.36 (on a 5-point scale), Portugal showed strong agreement with positive statements about the application, and Spain recorded clearly positive evaluations. This cross-country consistency validates the application's effectiveness across different linguistic and pedagogical contexts.

Belgium (French): Teachers found the yardstick-based analysis and grammatical complexity tools (such as coordination and auxiliaries) very useful. However, they requested more direct alternative text suggestions and noted that the Writing Assistant interface could sometimes feel "overcharged" with information.

Portugal (Portuguese): Users reported that the tool effectively supported reflection on text simplification strategies. A need was identified for greater familiarity with the underlying linguistic concepts of the indicators, suggesting the value of accompanying training materials.

Spain (Spanish): Participants found the lexical analysis easiest to understand, though some metalinguistic terms presented challenges. Teachers expressed particular interest in using the software for collective classroom work rather than just individual lesson preparation, indicating potential for expanded pedagogical applications.

Key Cross-Country Findings

The European-wide testing validated several important aspects of the iRead4Skills application:

- **Usability:** The web-based interface proved accessible to educators across different countries and technical skill levels
- **Interpretability:** The Text Classifier's global assessments were well understood, while the Writing Assistant's detailed indicators required some training for optimal use
- **Pedagogical Adequacy:** Both tools were judged appropriate for adult education contexts, with teachers identifying clear applications in material preparation and classroom activities
- **Cross-linguistic Validity:** The framework's three complexity levels (Very Easy, Easy, Plain) proved applicable across French, Portuguese, and Spanish

6. Website Usage Statistics

The iRead4Skills system usage, besides the testing phase, was tracked through Google Analytics from **1 January 2025 to 9 February 2026**. The analytics concern the most recent and stable prototype version available online only, and not the version(s) used for co-creation workshops or early training and dissemination actions. The data provides valuable insights into user engagement, geographic reach, and application feature usage, as the dissemination of the project grows and gathers more engagement.

6.1 User Overview

The application recorded **155 active users** across four countries during the reporting period. User engagement was strong, with an average interaction time of 14 minutes and 4 seconds per active user and an average of 2.3 sessions with interaction per user. The user base was predominantly female (63.5%), reflecting the gender composition of the adult education workforce.

6.2 Geographic Reach

Country	Active Users
Portugal	104
Spain	34

Belgium	15
France	2

The most active cities were Lisbon (31 users), Cerdanyola del Vallès (21 users), Barreiro (17 users), and Almada (11 users) in the Lisbon metropolitan area; Ottignies-Louvain-la-Neuve (8 users) and Charleroi (5 users) in Belgium; and Barcelona (5 users) in Spain.

6.3 Application Feature Usage

The event tracking data reveals how users engaged with the core application functions:

Event Name	Event Count
portuguese_analysis	876
page_view	765
scroll	729
french_analysis	928
user_engagement	610
session_start	560

The data shows that Portuguese text analysis was the most-used feature (876 events), followed by French text analysis (928 events combined). This indicates strong adoption of the text classification functionality across both language versions. The high number of scroll events (729) and user engagement events (610) suggests that users actively explored the application's outputs and results.

6.4 User Retention and Loyalty

User loyalty metrics demonstrate healthy engagement patterns:

- Daily Active Users / Monthly Active Users (DAU/MAU): 5.7%
- Daily Active Users / Weekly Active Users (DAU/WAU): 15.6%
- Weekly Active Users / Monthly Active Users (WAU/MAU): 36.8%

6.5 Language Diversity

Active users accessed the application in multiple languages, with Portuguese being the predominant language, followed by Spanish, English, French, and Catalan. This multilingual user base confirms the application's cross-linguistic appeal and validates the project's approach of developing tools for multiple Romance languages.

6.6 Continuous Monitoring

The iRead4Skills APP Monitoring Form - a structured instrument designed to capture detailed feedback on application functionality, usability, and performance - is available in all four project languages (English, French, Portuguese, and Spanish) through the project website (iread4skills.com/tools/).

7. Key Activities for User Engagement

Activity	Date	Engagement numbers
Co-Creation Session at UNOVA	17 February 2025	13 teachers from 6 schools
Accredited Training Session 1	25 November 2024	160 participants from PT
Accredited Training Session 2	29 April 2025	152 participants from PT, BR, AO, GW, MZ
Text Classification Testing (5 sessions)	8-30 May 2025	Partner schools + Ler+Qualifica network
Pedagogical Days (2 events)	July 2025	AE Paço de Arcos + AE Adelaide Cabette
III Meeting Santiago de Compostela	July 2025	7 partner school teachers
Accredited Training Session 3	14 December 2025	110 participants, hands-on prototype testing
Prototype Testing Period	15 Dec 2025 – 27 Jan 2026	133 teachers + 290 learners systematic testing
Prototype Testing Session	22 January 2026	23 teachers from 6 partner schools
TOTAL USERS/PARTICIPANTS		+897

8. Final Remarks

The implementation of the iRead4Skills project has achieved remarkable success in engaging the target end-user community through comprehensive training actions and systematic application testing across Europe, and beyond. The project's approach, combining large-scale accredited training with hands-on co-creation, iterative testing, and web platform monitoring, has proven highly effective in ensuring both broad reach and meaningful engagement, with foreseeable results for the future.

The system testing demonstrated strong user endorsement, with 92% usability approval and 89% educational relevance ratings. Educators praised the tool's intuitive interface and pedagogical value, while the participation of adult learners validated that the tools were tested with their intended target audience. The teachers and trainers who participated represented a diverse range of educational offerings, including AL courses, VET programmes, literacy and language courses, citizenship education, and digital skills training.

Web platform analytics confirm sustained engagement beyond the formal testing phases, with 155 active users across four countries performing 1,804 text analyses (876 Portuguese + 928 French) and demonstrating an average interaction time of over 14 minutes per session. User loyalty metrics (WAU/MAU of 36.8%) indicate healthy recurring engagement patterns.

The co-creation approach adopted by the project, exemplified by the February 2025 session at UNOVA, the brainstorming sessions at the Santiago de Compostela meeting, and the Pedagogical Days at partner schools, has been instrumental in ensuring that the application meets real classroom needs.

In conclusion, this user report shows that the iRead4Skills project has successfully demonstrated both the demand for and the feasibility of the developed tools in adult education.